

Sun Protection Factor (SPF) Determination of Cosmetic Formulations Made in Kinshasa (DR Congo) by In-Vitro Method using UV-VIS Spectrophotometer

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ABSTRACT

The increasing consumer awareness on the risk of sun exposure related diseases like skin cancer etc., leads to the cosmetic formulation be approximately tested and Sun protection factor (SPF) claimed. The efficiency of the cosmetic formulation depends on the SPF value. Due to high cost and time consumption of in vivo SPF determination methods, in vitro methods are gaining more importance. The aim of this study is to determine the SPF of somebody creams and lotions made in Kinshasa by Ultraviolet-Visible spectrophotometry. Fourteen different commercially somebody creams and lotions made in Kinshasa by various manufacturers were procured and calculated SPF evaluated. The calculated SPF values were in the range of 0.30 to 21.84. It is observed that the proposed spectrophotometric method is simple, rapid and repeatable for the in vitro determination of SPF values of sunscreen products.

Keywords: In vitro SPF, UV-Vis spectroscopy, cosmetic formulations.

INTRODUCTION

Every year, more than one million people are diagnosed with skin cancer and about 1% dies from malignant melanoma. Most skin cancer occur on the areas that are most frequently exposed to the sun, such as the face, neck, head and the back of the hands [1-5].

The human skin consists of three layers: the epidermis, the dermis and the subcutis. This architecturally structure of 1.5 to 2 m² of surface area is pliable and has the intrinsic properties to protect itself from the sun, the melanin [5,6].

Thus, the skin is the body's first line of defense for external exposure with melanin as the skin natural sunscreen. But excessive radiations of sunrays are unprotected and can lead to painful sunburn or other skin related complication [5].

In fact, acute and chronic exposure to non-physiological doses of ultraviolet radiation leads to variety of changes of skin. It is well known that overexposure to the sunlight, particularly to the UV rays, may cause many skin defects, like sunburns (erythema), premature skin aging (winkles), photosensitivity, suppression of the immune system or even skin cancer.

Ultraviolet radiation (UVR) is a part of the electromagnetic spectrum that lies in the range of 200 and 400 nm and it is divided arbitrarily into three regions: UVA, from 400 to 320 nm; UVB, from 320 to 290 nm and UVC, from 290 to 200 nm. UVC radiation is filtered out by the atmosphere before reaching earth. UVB radiation is not completely filtered out by the ozone layer and is responsible for the damage due to sunburn and pyrimidine dimers. UVA radiation reaches the deeper layers of the epidermis and dermis and provokes the premature ageing of the skin and is responsible for the generation of free radicals and others effects.

The UVR-induced skin effects acute responses such as inflammation, erythema, pigmentation, hyperplasia, immunosuppression, vitamin D synthesis and chronic effects such

as photocarcinogenesis and photoaging. UVB radiation may promote a deficit in the immunologic functions of the skin in the addition to the anomalies in the DNA, thus the abnormal cells that should be destroyed may be tolerated and can divide and replicate giving rise to the formation of a cancer. UVB radiation is involved in 65% damage of all skin [5, 7- 10].

The signs of ageing skin are the most visible in the skin. Although, ageing skin is not a threat of a person, it can have a detrimental effect on the psychology of a person. Much of the premature ageing occurs as a direct or indirect result of skin's interaction with environment [4,5].

For skin protection from deleterious effects of sunlight, cosmetic formulations are used in various form having chemical filters, physical filters and/or herbal extracts. The molecules in sunscreen absorb most of UVB and prevent it from reaching the skin just as the atmosphere molecules absorb UVC and prevent it from reaching the ground. Thus, chemical filters, physical filters and/or herbal extracts like sunscreen are now incorporated into everyday products such as moisturizers, creams, oil, gel, spray, lotions, shampoos, mousses, and other hair and skin formulations [5,9,12-15].

The effectiveness of a sunscreen is usually expressed by the sun protection factor (SPF) which is the ratio UV energy required to produce a minimal erythematous dose (MED) in protected skin to unprotected skin. The minimal erythematous dose is defined as the lowest time interval or dosage of UV light irradiation sufficient to produce a minimal, perceptible erythema on unprotected skin. The higher the SPF, the more effective is the product in preventing sunburn [3,8,9,16].

The regular use of these sunscreen formulations can help to reduce the chance of the harmful effects of ultraviolet radiation [10,13].

The photoprotection afforded by topical sunscreen against solar ultraviolet radiation exposure can be determined *in vivo* or *in vitro* by mean of SPF. The most traditional and officially accepted method in several countries is the *in vivo* method determination of SPF. These methods are long range methods and involve 10 to 15 human volunteers of both sexes, with appropriate skin type. This type of determination has been used for many years and although useful and precise, is a time consuming process, complex and expensive, particularly when information concerning to the protection against long wavelength (UVA) is required [3,17].

Consequently, much effort has been devoted to the development of *in vitro* techniques for assessing the photoprotection of sunscreen compounds. Thus, for economical, practical and ethical reasons, a suitable *in vitro* measurement of SPF is required, at least for screening or evaluating purposes, to minimize risks related to UV exposure of human subjects during a sunscreen product development. SPF is primarily a measure of UVB protection, as UVB is 1000 times more erythemogenic than UVA [9,14,15].

The *in vitro* methods are in general of two types. Methods which involve the measurement of absorption or the transmission of UV radiation through sunscreen formulation films in quartz plates or biomembranes, and methods in which the absorption characteristics of the sunscreens agents are determined based on spectrophotometric analysis of dilute solutions [3,9]

In a tropical country like Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), the exposure to UVA and UVB (sunlight) rays is a regular phenomenon. It becomes imperative that one takes adequate measures to protect their skin from burns/radiation, especially during the daytime when solar radiation is at its peak.

In Kinshasa, major town of (DRC) where there are more than ten million people, more than the half of people spend their time outdoor, under the sun at an average temperature of about 28°C. They are concern of sun overexposure and skin damaging. This town knows a rapid growth of commercially available cosmetic products of different manufacturers. The body creams and lotions used are made in Kinshasa and in foreigner. Unfortunately, there is no data available on the study of those cosmetic formulations made in Kinshasa, mainly on SPF. Only on a few cosmetic formulations came from foreigner the sun protection factor (SPF) is labeled. At the light of their importance for the human health, the SPF determination of these cosmetic formulations made in Kinshasa is required.

The goal of this research was to determine the *in vitro* SPF values of fourteen selected body creams and lotions made in Kinshasa containing plant extracts and/or chemical sunscreens through UV-Vis spectrophotometry and the application of the Mansur mathematical equation [3,9].

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Samples preparation.

Fourteen commercially available body creams and lotions of various manufacturers made in Kinshasa (samples MB1-MB14) and two samples that came from foreigner (MB15 and MB16) were purchased from Kinshasa market. 1.0 g of all samples was weighed, transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask, diluted to volume with ethanol (Merck product, analytical grade), followed by ultrasonication for 5 min and then filtered through cotton, rejecting the ten first ml. A 10 ml aliquot was transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask and diluted to volume with ethanol. Then a 10 ml

aliquot was transferred to a 50 ml volumetric flask and the volume completed with ethanol.

Spectrophotometric measurement and SPF determination

The absorption spectra of samples in solution were obtained in the range of 290 to 320 nm, every 5 nm using a Hitachi U-3900 H. UV/Visible spectrophotometer, equipped with 1 cm quartz cell and a computer. Three determinations were made at each point using ethanol as a blank.

SPF values were determined using Mansur equation (equation 1) [3,9]. Indeed, Mansur *et al.*, developed a very simple mathematical equation which substitutes the *in vitro* method proposed by Sayre *et al.*, utilizing UV spectrophotometry and the following equation 1 [3,9].

$$SPF_{spectrophotometric} = CF \times \sum_{290}^{320} EE(\lambda) \times I(\lambda) \times Abs(\lambda) \quad (1)$$

Where EE: erythemal effect spectrum; I : solar intensity spectrum; Abs: absorbance of sunscreen product ; CF: correction factor (= 10).

The values of EE x I are constants and predetermined by Sayre *et al.* [3,9] and are showed in Table 1.

Table 1: Normalized product function used in the calculation of SPF [3,8,9].

Wavelength (nm)	EE X I (normalized)
290	0,0150
295	0,0817
300	0,2874
305	0,3278
310	0,1864
315	0,0837
320	0,0180
Total	1

EE: erythemal effect spectrum; I: solar intensity spectrum

The most used classification of phototypes is the Fitzpatrick's which is based on the first 30-45 minutes of sun exposure after a winter season of no sun exposure, as presented on Table 2 [13].

Table 2: Fitzpatrick's classification of skin prototypes.

Prototype	Recommended SPF
I	40
II	20-40
III	7-20
IV	6-15
V	5-10
VI	4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The calculated SPF value of sixteen different commercially formulations results are shown in table 3 along with the information related to the presence of active ingredients.

Table 3: Active ingredient and calculated SPF values of the commercially available formulations made in Kinshasa and those coming from foreigner.

Samples	Active Ingredients	Calculated SPF
MB 1*	Mineral oil, jojoba oil, Allantoin	17.90±0.33
MB 2*	Allantoin	9.76±0.10
MB 3*	sunscreen	19.32±0.29
MB 4**	Non specified	20.52±0.71
MB 5**	Coconut extracts	21.84±0.40
MB 6**	Allantoin	19.59±0.71
MB 7**	Mineral oil, alce barbadensis leaf, Allantoin	12.62±0.54
MB 8**	Carrot oil	15.74±0.27
MB 9**	p-chloro-m-cresol, lemon extracts	10.48±0.41
MB 10**	Mineral oil, carrot extracts, fruits acid extracts	13.41±0.44
MB 11****	Mineral oil, almond oil	0.50±0.04
MB 12****	Mineral oil, almond oil	0.54±0.06
MB 13****	Mineral oil	0.40±0.04
MB 14****	Mineral oil	0.30±0.06
MB 15****	Anthemisa nobillis flower oil, olea Europea oil	1.72±0.08
MB 16****	Ethyl hexyl salicylate, aloe vera	4.95±0.03

*: formulations with sunscreen claimed made in Kinshasa
 **: formulations without sunscreen claimed made in Kinshasa
 ***: babies' formulations made in Kinshasa
 ****: babies' and Kid's formulations came from foreigner.

Fourteen of sixteen samples are made in Kinshasa (MB1-MB14), two came from foreigner (MB15 and MB16) and six are kid's or babies' lotions (MB11- MB16). Three chemical filters are used and plant extracts. The calculated SPF values were in the range of 0, 30 to 21, 84. Samples have one, two or three actives ingredients. Four samples over sixteen used allantoin. Seven samples over sixteen used mineral oil. Six samples over sixteen used essentials oil. One sample has active ingredients not specified.

On sixteen samples (MB1-MB16), six had $SPF < 5$, (MB11-MB16); one had $5 < \text{calculated SPF value} < 10$, (MB2); three had $10 < \text{calculated SPF value} < 15$ (MB7, MB9, MB10) and six had $SPF > 15$ (MB1, MB3, MB4, MB5, MB6 and MB8). Figure 1 show percentage of categorization of sample depending to SPF values.

Figure 1: Proportions of calculated SPF values cosmetic formulations.

Figure 2: SPF values of kids' of babies' formulation samples Babies or kids samples have calculated SPF value lower than 5. All babies' formulations made in Kinshasa had calculated SPF value lower than 1.

Measurement of SPF is ultimate way to determine effectiveness of sunscreen formulation. The higher the SPF, the more protection a sunscreen offers against UV-light. Sunscreens are used to aid the body's natural defense mechanisms to protect against harmful UV radiation from the sun. Its function is based on its ability to absorb, reflect or scatter the sun's rays [20].

In this work, the *in vitro* SPF of sixteen different commercially available cosmetic formulations made in Kinshasa named from sample MB1 to sample MB16 were evaluated by UV-visible spectrophotometry applying Mansur mathematical equation. It can be observed that the calculated SPF values found for samples MB1-MB10 are more than five. All other samples presented calculated SPF values lower than five (MB11-MB16) (Table 3 and figure 1). Sample MB8 have an optimal SPF value i.e. 15.74. Among samples analyzed, sample MB5 exhibits a maximal absorbance higher than all samples of cosmetic formulations, as it can be observed in Table 3. This is probably due to the fact this sample have more coconut extracts amount, presenting thus, a calculated SPF higher than the others.

Samples MB11 and MB12 presented nearly the same calculated SPF values ($SPF \sim 0, 50$). They have the same active ingredients perhaps in different amount. Sample MB13 and MB14 have the same active ingredients. The active ingredient amount in the sample MB13 can be enough like reflected in the obtained calculated SPF value.

All samples have different calculated SPF (samples MB1-MB16); data variation can be due to the composition of those formulations. As it can be seen in figure 2, samples MB11-MB16 have the calculated SPF values lower than 5. This should be an alert since formulations with SPF more than 30 are greatly used in phototype I that includes babies, children, persons with clear skin, persons who cannot be exposed directly to the sunlight and also professionals of outdoor exposure like fisherman, building workers, street sellers, policeman and lifeguards must [13].

Samples MB1-MB10 have the calculated SPF values more than 10 except MB2 which has calculated SPF 9.76. According to the Fitzpatrick's classification of the phototype [13] and at the light of the calculated SPF values, cosmetic formulations made in Kinshasa are suitable for more than 50% of Kinshasa's people. Efforts are recommended about people of Fitzpatrick's prototype I and II classification.

The *in vivo* SPF determination is not concern in Kinshasa. Only the *in vitro* SPF determination is possible. At the light of calculated SPF values found in this research in comparison with the literature [3,9,13,17,20], the samples MB1, MB3 and MB6 having calculated SPF value 17.90; 19.32 and 19.59 respectively could have labeled SPF 20. The samples MB4 and MB5 where calculated SPF value are 20.52 and 21.84 respectively could have labeled SPF 30 or more than 30. The calculated SPF value 15.74 and 13.41 respectively for the samples MB8 and MB 10 could have labeled SPF 15. The samples MB2, MB7 and MB9 having calculated SPF value 9.76; 12.62 and 10.48 respectively could have labeled SPF 10.

There are many factors affecting the determination of SPF values, for example, no applicability of proper methods for evaluation of sunscreen products, the combination and concentration of the sunscreen, the use of different solvents in which the sunscreen are dissolved; the type of emulsion; the effects and interactions of vehicle components, such as esters, emollients and emulsifiers used in the formulation; the interaction of the vehicle with the skin; the addition of other active ingredients; the pH system, viscosity and the emulsion rheological properties, among other factors, which can increase or decrease UV absorption of each sunscreen [3,9].

The effect that different solvents and emollients have upon the wavelength of maximum absorbance and upon the UV absorbance of several sunscreens chemical, alone or in combination is well known and documented [1,3,4,8,15,17,19,21]. Excipients and other active ingredients can also produce UV absorption bands, thus interfering with those of UVA and UVB sunscreen. Thus, this effect can be reflected in a finished formulation, especially for the six creams with a calculated SPF greater than 15. The effect of a solvent is only realized at high percentages [3].

Therefore, to develop cosmetic formulations with better safety and high SPF that can be used by Fitzpatrick's prototype I and II classification, the formulator must understand the physicochemical principle, not only the UV absorbance of the actives, but also vehicle components, such as esters, emollients and emulsifiers used in the formulation. This, since sunscreen can interact with other components of the vehicle, and these interactions can affect sunscreen efficacy [8,17,19].

Every year, statistical data indicates an increase of skin cancer incidence; this is contradictory when we think of many products available on the market with useful information and high performance sunscreens. On the other hand, it is important that the chosen SPF be correct for each individual's phototype. The application of sunscreens should be done correctly (over the entire body, before sun exposure and reapplied regularly) and in a correct amount, around 2g/cm² [13].

CONCLUSIONS

The calculated SPF values of the analyzed samples are in the range of 0.30 to 21.84. The sample MB14 presented the lowest calculated SPF (SPF= 0.3) and the sample MB5 the greatest calculated SPF (SPF= 21.84). All babies' and kids samples have

calculated SPF values lower than 5. The cosmetic formulations made in Kinshasa are suitable for more than 50% of Kinshasa's people at the light of the calculated SPF and the Fitzpatrick prototype classification. The proposed UV spectrophotometric method is easy, rapid, employs low cost reagents and can be used for the *in vitro* determination of SPF values in many cosmetic formulations. The proposed methodology may be useful as a rapid quality control tool. It can be used during the production process, in the analysis of the final product, and can give important information before proceeding to the *in vivo* tests.

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